

EVALUATION OF RESERVOIR SATURATION USING METHODS OF MINING GEOPHYSICS**Hasanov Adalat Badal***Professor, Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University,
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Azerbaijan 20, ave. Azadlig, Baku, AZ1010***Abstract**

The article is devoted to the evaluation of reservoir rock saturation using well logging methods in petroleum geophysics. The main objective of the study is to determine porosity, shale content, and fluid saturation of formations based on well logging data. The paper analyzes the interpretation principles of gamma ray logging, neutron logging, electrical and induction logging, as well as other integrated geophysical methods. As an example petrophysical parameters were calculated to determine the oil, gas, and water saturation of the formations, and the obtained results were comparatively evaluated. Also the capabilities and limitations of geophysical methods under various geological conditions were discussed. Reflected that using of modern geophysical technologies, high-precision logging systems, and digital interpretation software not only ensures the scientific validity of saturation assessment but also contributes to more accurate reserve estimation, the timely identification of non-productive and low-productive zones. Obtaining results of the study contribute to refining reservoir quality assessment and support effective decision-making in field development.

Keywords: petroleum geophysics, well logging, reservoir, saturation, saturation, porosity, shale content.

Mining geophysics is one of the key scientific and applied disciplines in the modern oil and gas industry, aimed at studying the petrophysical properties of reservoir rocks and evaluating the degree of saturation of formations with oil, gas, and water [1-4]. The efficient development of hydrocarbon deposits, accurate estimation of reserves, and optimization of development projects directly depend on the precise determination of reservoir quality indicators, particularly porosity, permeability, and saturation parameters [5, 6].

In this context, geophysical investigations carried out in boreholes; especially well logging methods, serve as one of the most important sources of continuous and real-time information about the physical properties of formations [7-9]. The concept of saturation in reservoir rocks characterizes the relative proportion of fluids—oil, gas, and water—contained within the pore volume. Although total saturation represents the sum of all fluids in the pore space, from an industrial perspective the most significant indicators are the oil and gas saturation coefficients.

The water saturation coefficient, in turn, is considered a key parameter both for evaluating reservoir efficiency and for estimating reserves [2]. The saturation characteristics of a formation vary depending on the lithological composition of the rock, pore structure, degree of cementation, content of clay minerals, as well as capillary pressure and electrical properties. Therefore, the evaluation of saturation requires a comprehensive approach and the integration of several geophysical methods.

The most widely used methods for determining saturation in mining geophysics are electrical and induction logging, neutron logging, and gamma logging [4, 5]. Electrical and induction methods measure the specific electrical resistivity of a formation, providing information about the

conductivity of the fluid contained in the pore spaces. It is well known that when the mineralization of formation water is high, its electrical conductivity increases; consequently, as water saturation increases, the overall resistivity of the rock decreases.

Neutron logging is primarily sensitive to the hydrogen content of the rock and plays an important role in determining porosity. Since the amount of hydrogen atoms is closely related to the volume of fluid in the pores, the neutron method provides information about both porosity and, indirectly, saturation. In gas-bearing formations, a decrease in neutron log readings is known as the “gas effect,” and this feature is considered an important diagnostic indicator for identifying gas reservoirs.

Gamma logging measures the natural radioactivity of rocks and makes it possible to evaluate clay content. Accurate determination of clay content is essential for calculating saturation, as the clay fraction reduces effective pore volume and influences electrical measurements.

During petrophysical modeling, laboratory analyses, geophysical well logging data, and hydrodynamic parameters are considered together. Total and effective porosity are distinguished, cementation and tortuosity factors are taken into account, and capillary pressure curves are utilized. Digital interpretation software enables the correlation of various logging curves. This allowing a more accurate determination of the lithological model of the formation and the distribution of fluids.

The complexity of the geological environment is one of the key factors that directly and multifaceted influences the accurate evaluation of reservoir saturation. In particular, in carbonate reservoir rocks, widely developed fracture systems and dual porosity lead to an uneven distribution of fluids within the formation. This creates additional uncertainties in the

interpretation of geophysical parameters such as electrical resistivity, density, and neutron porosity. In terrigenous rocks, heterogeneity, variability in grain composition, differences in the degree of cementation, and abrupt changes in stratification can reduce the accuracy of empirical relationships used in determining saturation. As a result, the same geophysical parameter may have different physical meanings under different geological conditions, making the interpretation process more complex and multi-variant.

Therefore, it is essential that geophysical data be consistently integrated with the geological model, meaning that lithological, petrophysical, and structural characteristics must be analyzed in a comprehensive manner. Structural and tectonic features—such as faults, flexures, block structures, and zones of tectonic stress—have a significant impact on both the distribution and filtration properties of reservoirs. At the same time, facies variations and sedimentation conditions lead to spatial changes in the porosity and permeability of rocks. For example, reservoir properties of rocks formed in coastal-marine environments can differ significantly from those deposited in deep-marine settings. All these factors collectively have a direct influence on reservoir quality, saturation characteristics, and production potential.

One of the most important tasks facing modern mining geophysics during drilling is the accurate identification of oil and gas-bearing formations and the evaluation of their productivity. Determining the saturation characteristics of reservoirs (oil, gas, or water) is not achieved through a single method, but rather through the integrated analysis of mud logging (gas logging) and geophysical well logging data. This approach allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the geological section and helps minimize uncertainties that may arise during drilling.

Gas logging is based on studying the quantity and composition of hydrocarbon gases present in the

drilling fluid circulating during the drilling process [5]. The main advantage of this method is its ability to provide data in real time. As the rock is broken, the fluids it contains enter the drilling mud and are recorded at the surface using gas analyzers. The ratio of methane and its homologs (ethane, propane, butane) helps provide a preliminary assessment of whether the formation is oil-bearing or gas-bearing. A sharp increase in gas readings is a direct indication of entering a reservoir zone. However, since the parameters of the drilling fluid and technological factors can influence these readings, they must be taken into account. One of the most important tasks facing modern mining geophysics during drilling is the accurate identification of oil and gas-bearing formations and the evaluation of their productivity. Determining the saturation characteristics of reservoirs (oil, gas, or water) cannot be achieved using a single method; rather, it requires the integrated analysis of mud logging (gas logging) and geophysical well logging data. This approach makes it possible to obtain more comprehensive information about the geological section and to minimize uncertainties that may arise during drilling.

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Fig. 1. Diagram of complex assessment of reservoir saturation based on gas logging and geophysical logging

The figure presents the results of comprehensive geophysical well logging studies in the form of a multi-track diagram, allowing the evaluation of the lithological structure of formations, their physical properties, and fluid saturation. On the left side, the depth scale of the well (approximately 3500–3730 m interval) is shown. Next to it, technological parameters—particularly the rate of penetration (DMK) during drilling and the condition of the drilling tool—are provided. These data give a preliminary understanding of rock strength and drilling conditions. The next track displays the lithological section, where different symbols are used to distinguish sandy, clayey, and layered rocks. This column helps in the initial differentiation between reservoir and non-reservoir intervals. In the middle section, geophysical logging curves are presented: Gamma-ray logging (GR) indicates the natural radioactivity of the rock and is mainly used to evaluate clay content (higher GR corresponds to higher clay content). Electrical resistivity logs (R10, R28) reflect the electrical properties of the formation; high resistivity is typically associated with oil or gas saturation, while low resistivity indicates water saturation. On the right side, density logging and porosity (Kp) curves are shown. These parameters make it possible to assess pore volume and reservoir quality. The rightmost track represents gas logging results, showing the total gas

content as well as variations in individual components (C1 – methane, C2 – ethane, C3–C5, etc.). An increase in gas components indicates entry into reservoir zones and the presence of hydrocarbons. Overall, the figure is used to identify reservoir intervals and evaluate their porosity and saturation characteristics (oil, gas, or water) based on the integrated interpretation of geophysical and gas logging data.

Overall, the evaluation of reservoir saturation using mining geophysical methods is a complex, multi-stage process that requires a scientifically grounded and integrated approach. This process includes the collection of initial data, quality control, comparative analysis of different geophysical methods, construction of petrophysical models, and final interpretation. The use of modern technologies such as high-precision logging tools, digital interpretation software, and 3D geological modeling systems significantly improves the reliability of the results. In addition, the application of integrated interpretation methods enables more accurate reserve estimation, timely identification of non-productive or low-productive intervals for exclusion from production, and optimization of reservoir development strategies.

The integrated application of various geophysical methods, as well as the correlation of the obtained results with geological and petrophysical data, enables a more accurate, objective, and reliable determination

of saturation in water, oil, and gas reservoirs. This approach is not limited to the results of individual methods; it also involves a multiparameter interpretation that takes into account lithological, structural, tectonic, and stratigraphic characteristics. This helps to overcome the difficulties caused by geological complexity, such as fracturing and dual porosity in carbonate rocks, as well as heterogeneity and layered variability in terrigenous formations.

Using of modern geophysical technologies, high-precision logging systems, and digital interpretation software not only ensures the scientific validity of saturation assessment but also contributes to more accurate reserve estimation, the timely identification of non-productive and low-productive zones. Additionally it lead to the efficient and rational development of hydrocarbon fields, thereby significantly reducing economic and operational risks in the oil and gas industry.

References

1. Abbasov E.Y., et al. Detailed geological and tectonic study of the Khara-Zira structure and surrounding territories of South Caspian Basin based on seismic-velocity models. *Geology and Geophysics of Russian South* 16 (1) 2026, pp. 121-133
2. Abbasov, O.R. *Geophysical Methods of Well Investigation*. Baku: ASOIU, 2016.
3. Dakhnov, V.N. *Geophysical Methods for Determining Reservoir Properties and Oil and Gas Saturation of Rocks*. Moscow: Nedra, 1985.
4. Dobrynin, V.M., Vendelstein, B.Yu., Kozhevnikov, D.A. *Petrophysics*. Moscow: Nedra, 2011.
5. Ellis, D.V., Singer, J.M. *Well Logging for Earth Scientists*. 2nd Edition. Dordrecht: Springer, 2007.
6. Hasanov A.B., et al. Stability conditions of oil-saturated reservoirs porosity with deep overlying. *ANAS Transactions, Earth Sciences*, No. 2, 2022, pp. 46-53, DOI: 10.33677/ggianas20220200081.
7. Rider, M., Kennedy, M. *The Geological Interpretation of Well Logs*. 3rd Edition. Rider-French Consulting Ltd., 2011.
8. Zaalishvili V.B., et al. Detailing the pore structure of productive intervals of oil wells using the Color 3D Imaging. *Energies*, Vol. 16, No. 1, 217, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16010217>.
9. Zalyaev, R.R. *Interpretation of Well Logging Data*. Moscow: Nedra, 2014.